

THE ROLE OF "LEARNING APPS" PORTAL IN GEOGRAPHY EDUCATION

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Annotation

This article provides information about the educational modules created using the LearningApps electronic educational resource for teaching the subject of "World Economic and Social Geography" in general secondary schools and its contribution to the increase in educational efficiency.

Keywords: information and communication technologies, pedagogical technologies, online education, electronic educational resources, LearningApps, QR code, portal.

Introduction

In the world, recent developments on the field of education creates the need to improve the teaching of subjects on the basis of interactive methods, information and communication and pedagogical technologies. The subject of "World Economic and Social Geography" taught in general secondary schools studies the laws of territorial organization of the world's natural resources, population and economy from an economic and social point of view. This subject is a great opportunity for the further integration of our country with the countries of the world. In such conditions, the importance of the subject "World economic and social geography" taught in general secondary schools is becoming more relevant.

The importance of the problem of further improvement of the effectiveness of teaching the subject of "World Economic and Social Geography" in general secondary schools, the lack of implementation of innovative pedagogical technologies in educational practice, the creation of electronic resources used in teaching the subject, for online education the need to create applications, create and develop a methodology for its use, lack of methodological manuals and recommendations prepared on the basis of new methods and innovative pedagogical technologies creates the need to develop scientific and methodological research in this research direction.

Organization of the knowledge acquired by students in the subject of "World Economic and Social Geography" in accordance with modern pedagogical technologies, scientific and creative organization, identification of ways to solve problems by creating unusual situations for students and implementation of ways to solve them formation of practical skills is one of the most important issues.

- Analysis of literature on the topic

In general secondary education, if we use information and communication technologies and multimedia applications, educational motivation and cognitive activity of students will be increased.

Nowadays, LearningApps is one of the electronic resources widely used in the education of the countries of the world.

LearningApps is a program, i.e. a portal, for organizing the learning and teaching process through small, interactive, multimedia learning modules (Fig. 1). Learning modules can be embedded directly into the curriculum and users can create or modify them themselves. It is also possible to complete each training task by QR code.

Figure 1. LearningApps portal interface.

Allows you to create and use multimedia applications using the LearningApps portal. Exercises related to any subject can be performed. The portal is available in English, German, French, Italian, Spanish and Russian. Also, students who create and perform tasks have opportunities to work in text, image, audio and video formats.

Also, the use of information and communication technologies in education leads to the following results:

- allows students to think freely;
- develops language skills;
- teaches to express one's opinion, to search in every way;
- increases creative activity and educates to work together in a team;
- forms an educated person who learns on his own and is well versed in information technologies.

- **Research methodology**

The LearningApps portal offers more than 20 learning modules, templates, a range of collaboration tools, and a framework for designing educational games for developers. Templates can be divided into the following 6 groups according to their function:

The authoring tool now offers more than 20 templates for learning building blocks, a range of collaboration tools, and a framework for designing educational games for developers. Task types of templates can be divided into 6 groups:

- 1) *Selection tasks* (multiple selection, closing the text, highlighting in the text)
- 2) *Assignments* (assigning pairs, assignments on pictures, assignments on the map, assignments for groups)
- 3) *Sequence tasks* (sequence or order, series of numbers)
- 4) *Writing tasks* (fill in the blank, quiz, crossword, table)
- 5) *Multiplayer tasks* (ordering, guessing, what's where?, quiz)
- 6) *Tools* (application matrix, audio-video overlay, chat, collaborative writing, calendar, mind map, notebook, bulletin board).

- **Analysis and results**

Teaching the subjects of "World Economic and Social Geography" using the portal provides good results. It is advisable to use the information on this portal in the homework part of the

lesson or in the reinforcement part of the lesson. Using the "LearningApps" portal, the following "mosaic" task can be used in the course of teaching the topic "National and religious structure of the world's population" (Fig. 2).

Figure 2. "National and religious composition of the world's population" on the "LearningApps" portal mosaic task created on the basis of the theme.

In this educational assignment, tasks are given in the columns "World religions", "World races", "Age and sex composition of the population", "Ethnic composition of the population and nationalities", "Location of the population". Students should choose mosaic windows in accordance with the above columns. If the column and the picture or word in the window match, it will be opened. Taskers perform tasks in the mosaic window based on the sequence in the columns, and the background image begins to unfold (Figure 3). Completing the task requires students to be thorough and think logically.

Figure 3. The final part of the mosaic task created on the "LearningApps" portal on the topic "National and religious structure of the world's population".

In the modern world, the form of distance education is also widely implemented. In such conditions, the LearningApps portal serves as a good tool for home, distance and online learners. When the student studies the topic "National and religious composition of the world's population", the task can be completed using the QR code (<https://learningapps.org/view27365788>) (Fig. 4). This will provide practical help to ensure that the information is more complete and understandable for students. Also, students can repeat tasks.

Figure 4. QR code

- **Conclusion and recommendations**

(Conclusion/Recommendations).

During the lesson, students perform the above tasks in the part of asking or strengthening the homework of the specified topic. Completing such tasks increases students' interest in geography.

As a result of completing this multimedia application, the ability of thinking independently will be improved. Students can express their opinion freely. The ability to work with information and communication technologies is developed.

We can see that the interest of students in independent research in geography has increased even more in lessons conducted with the help of innovative pedagogical technologies from the above electronic educational resources. Incorporation of studied geographic materials increases the reliability of information about the acquisition of a specific material and expands the possibilities of the management process.

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